

the brown planthopper and moderate resistance to green leafhopper and yellow stem borer. It is resistant to gall midge in several states of India.

In field tests, IR42 outyielded most IRRI varieties and elite lines on nutrient-deficient or toxic wetland rice soils and responded well to moderate

applications of nitrogen and phosphorus fertilizers.

Because it combines high yield potential with pest resistance and tolerance for nutrient deficiencies and soil toxicities (see table), IR42 may be a solution to the small rice farmer's problems. ■

GENETIC EVALUATION AND UTILIZATION

Deep water

Miniature deepwater tanks for screening chemicals against ufra

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Miniature deepwater tanks can be made from plastic soil pipe, 10 cm (4 inches) in diameter, cut into 1-m lengths. The pipes are sealed at the bottom with polythene and mounted upright in large earthenware pots of soil (see figure). Such tanks were used to determine the dosage of carbofuran needed to control ufra disease of deepwater rice, caused by the stem nematode *Ditylenchus angustus*,

after the appearance of symptoms in the vegetative phase.

Diseased tillers (those that exhibited early symptoms of attack, a faint chlorotic splash pattern on the young leaves) were transplanted from a field badly affected by ufra during August directly into the tubes at 3 tillers/tube. Furadan 3G was added to each tube at 1 of 5 rates (0, 1, 4, 7, 10 g), with 5 replications/rate, and the tubes were arranged in a 5 x 5 latin square. The water depth in each was maintained at 0.5 m. When the tubes were scored about 2 months later, symptoms were observed on 40% of the tillers in the control tubes, 35% in the tubes receiving 1 g of Furadan 3G, and none in the

other tubes. The chemotherapeutic effect of carbofuran is between 1 and 4 g of 3G granules/tube.

This simple technique may be adapted to screen many types of chemicals (applied as granule or foliar spray) for activity against ufra when the symptoms appear. It is superior to the use of inoculated tillers because the relationship between the nematode and its host develops under natural conditions until transplanting. It is also superior to field experimentation because reinfestation is completely excluded, the plot size can be reduced, and the number of replications can be increased correspondingly. ■

The ufra nematode population in deepwater rice in Bangladesh

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Ufra disease caused by the rice stem nematode *Ditylenchus angustus* devastates deepwater rice in southern Bangladesh. Infested crop residues cause primary infestation and water-borne inocula, secondary infestation during the growing season. Distinction between the two kinds of infestations is necessary when investigating the effect of treatments during land preparation. An examination of the nematode population in individual tillers during the vegetative phase can help in making such distinctions.

To determine the relative frequency of nematodes per individual tillers, a random sample of 50 tillers was taken from a field badly affected by ufra in Comilla district. Each tiller was cut off just below the top node, then truncated 15 cm above the node. Each segment was cut into 0.5-cm pieces and placed in a 7-ml bijou bottle with 2 ml water. After 24 hours the nematodes extracted by the water were counted with a Peters' 1-ml counting slide.

Three distinct modes in frequency distribution were found; the high mode was not continuous with the remainder

Miniature deepwater tanks for screening against ufra disease. Bangladesh Rice Research Institute.

The relative frequency of nematodes per tiller in a field in Comilla district, Bangladesh, 23 September 1978. Note: 16% of tillers were still not infested.

of the distribution (see figure). The crop is sown during the first rains, when no water stands in the fields. Nematodes have little chance of migrating from infested hills (primary infestation) to

nearby hills until the floods arrive 6 to 8 weeks later. The gap in the distribution represents the 2-month lag before secondary infestation by water-borne inocula can begin. With the advent of

floods, there is a burst of new infestation because the nematode population, although confined inside the primary infestation, has been growing. That accounts for the central mode in the population. Secondary infestation at initial flooding may cause the disease to spread over long distances. As the population continues to increase in primary and secondary infestations the nematodes spread through water, which accounts for the left-hand mode. This tertiary infestation consolidates the ufra patch.

If this Interpretation is correct, examination of the nematode population before panicle initiation will have several uses in ufra research: 1) to determine the inoculum source in experiments in farmers' fields (by presence or absence of the right-hand mode), 2) to distinguish between individual components of the nematode population growth rate, and particularly 3) to permit study of nematode population growth independently of the host's tillering behavior (by considering the rate at which the right-hand mode moves in that direction). ■

Flowering and yield response of late-maturing varieties under normal and waterlogged conditions

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Eighteen late-maturing varieties were tested under normal and waterlogged conditions (30–50 cm water depth) during 1977 kharif. The experiment was conducted in randomized blocks with 3 replications, fertilized with N, P₂O₅, and K₂O at 60-30-30 kg/ha.

Flowering was generally delayed under waterlogged conditions. The delay ranged from 1 to 11 days longer than under normal conditions (see table). Tiller number and yield were also reduced by waterlogging.

Only Panidhan 1, a selection of IR442, increased significantly in grain yield

Flowering and grain yield under normal and waterlogged conditions. Patna, India.

Designation	Parentage	Days (no.) to flowering		Yield (t/ha)		
		Normal	Water-logged	Normal	Water-logged	
IET3235	IR8/SLO13	125	126	5.0	4.4	
IET3236		124	126	4.3	4.0	
IET3257	CR63-3218-1/Pankaj	120	121	4.7	4.3	
IET3261	IR8/BJI/IR22	115	117	3.8	3.4	
IET4084	IET728/CR1014	122	123	4.1	3.8	
IET4086	CR36-48/CR70-80-2	108	119	4.1	3.8	
IET4087	CR63-5218-1/Pankaj	115	118	3.4	2.8	
IET5631	F1IR2042/CR94-13	122	124	4.5	3.8	
IET5633		122	123	4.1	3.3	
IET5638		114	115	4.5	3.8	
IET5656	RPW6-13/Sona	117	118	4.1	3.6	
IET5852	Pankaj/Jagannath	132	133	4.1	3.5	
IET5853		131	133	4.9	4.3	
IET5855	Sona/Mahsuri	125	126	4.4	3.8	
Intan		122	125	2.6	2.4	
Mahsuri		118	119	3.0	2.6	
Pankaj		116	118	5.0	4.1	
Panidhan-1	IR442 selection	102	104	2.0	2.3	
C.D. at 5%					0.60	0.52